

THE IMPORTANCE OF PEDAGOGICAL IDEAS IN INCLUDING THE PATRIOTIC SPIRIT IN YOUNG PEOPLE.

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Khasanov Nurmukhammad Khaydarali ugli

*Student of the military education faculty of Fergana State University
Uzbekistan, Fergana*

Yusufjonov Kuyoshbek Komiljon ugli

*Student of the military education faculty of Fergana State University
Uzbekistan, Fergana*

Annotation: *This article informs the importance of family, community and education in educating the young generation in the spirit of military patriotism, as well as the idea that the education of today's youth is one of the most responsible and urgent tasks, and the idea that the Motherland is one. It is about inculcating it in the minds and thinking of the rising generations.*

Keywords: *family, neighborhood, education, youth, personal education, social education, homeland, patriotism.*

Each science in the same object of study distinguishes its subject of research – one or another form of existence of the objective world, one or another side of the process of development of nature and society. Education as a complex, objectively existing phenomenon is studied by many Sciences. Historical materialism, for example, considers education as a particular moment in the development of society, its productive forces and relations of production; history as a particular moment in the history of class struggle and class politics; psychology - in connection with the study of the formation of the personality of a developing person. The independence of any science is determined, first of all, by the presence of a special, own subject of research, the presence of such a subject that is not specifically studied by any other scientific discipline.

In the General system of Sciences, in the General system of "things and knowledge", pedagogy is the only science that has as its subject the education of man.

The study of all science begins with the understanding of such questions: how did this science arise and develop, and what specific problems does it explore?

In fact, each science has its own history and a fairly specific aspect of natural or social phenomena, the study of which it is engaged and the knowledge of which is of great importance for understanding its theoretical foundations.

The isolation and formation of pedagogy as a science were caused by the growing needs of society in creating special educational institutions, in the theoretical understanding and generalization of spontaneously emerging experience of teaching and upbringing of younger generations, special preparation for life. Education and upbringing, thus, became an objective need of society and became the most important prerequisite for its development.

That is why at a certain stage of development of human society and, in particular, in the later period of the slave-owning system, when production and science have reached significant development, education is allocated to a special social function, that is, special educational institutions appear, there are people whose profession has become the education and upbringing of children. This was the case in many ancient countries, but more or less reliable information about schools for boys has come down to us from Egypt, the Middle East and ancient Greece.

I must say that already in the ancient world, many public figures and thinkers were well aware of and pointed out the huge role of education, both in the development of society and in the life of each person. For example, according to the laws of Solon (between 640 and 635-CA. 559 BC), it was assumed that the father must take care of special training of his sons in a particular field of work. As education expanded and became more complex, a special branch of theoretical knowledge related to educational activities began to be developed more intensively. This branch of knowledge, as well as knowledge in other spheres of life and production, was first developed in the depths of philosophy. Already in the works of ancient Greek philosophers-Heraclitus (530-470 BC), Democritus (460-early IV century BC), Socrates (469-399 BC), Plato (427-347 BC), Aristotle (384-322 BC), and others. – contained a lot of deep thoughts on issues of education. The term "pedagogy" also originates from ancient Greece, which has been established as the name of the science of education. How did this happen?

In Ancient Greece, teachers were slaves who were assigned by aristocrats to look after their children, accompany them to and from school, carry school supplies, and take walks with them. The Greek word "paidagogos" (pada – child, Gogo – news) is a "schoolmaster". In the future, teachers were called specially trained people who were engaged in teaching and raising children and for whom teaching was a profession. Hence the special science of education became known as pedagogy.

It should be said that many other pedagogical concepts and terms also originate from Ancient Greece, for example, school, which means "leisure", gymnasium - public school of physical education, and later just a secondary school, etc.

The issues of education also occupied a significant place in the works of ancient Roman philosophers and orators. Interesting pedagogical ideas, for example, were expressed by Lucretius Carus (CA. 99-55 BC), Quintilian (42-118 BC), and others.

In the middle ages, problems of education were developed by philosophers-theologians, whose pedagogical ideas were religious in color and were permeated with Church dogma.

Further development of pedagogical thought was received in the works of thinkers of the Renaissance (XIV-XVI centuries). The most prominent figures of this era - the Italian humanist Vittorio da Feltre (1378-1446), the Spanish philosopher and teacher Juan Vives (1442-1540), the Dutch thinker Erasmus of Rotterdam (1465-1536), and others.

They criticized the mechanical rote learning that flourished in education, advocated humane treatment of children, and the liberation of the individual from the shackles of oppression.

Despite the intensive development of educational theory, pedagogy continued to be a part of philosophy. As a special science pedagogy was first isolated from the system of philosophical knowledge at the beginning of the XVII century. Most researchers associate the design of pedagogy as an independent scientific discipline with the name of the great Czech teacher Jan Amos Comenius (1592-1670). The principles, methods, and forms of organization of educational work with children and moral education formulated by him became integral elements of subsequent scientific and pedagogical systems.

The works of such prominent figures as J. J. Rousseau (1712-1778), D. Diderot (1713-1784), K. A. Helvetius (1715-1771) in France, John Locke (1632-1704) in England, Johann Heinrich Pestalozzi (1746-1827) in Switzerland, Friedrich Adolf Wilhelm Diesterweg (1790-1866) and Johann Friedrich Herbart were of inestimable importance for the formation of scientific pedagogy (1776-1841) in Germany.

The founders of revolutionary demographic views in Russian pedagogy were V. G. Belinsky (1811-1848), A. I. Herzen (1812-1870), N. G. Chernyshevsky (1828-1889) and V. A. Dobrolyubov (1836-1861). The works of L. N. Tolstoy (1828-1910) and N. I. Pirogov (1810-1881) had a great influence on the formation of Russian scientific pedagogy. A complete, systematic disclosure of domestic pedagogical ideas was given in the works of K. D. Ushinsky (1824-1870). A great contribution to the development of Soviet pedagogy was made by N. K. Krupskaya (1869-1939), A.V. Lunacharsky (1875-1933), M. I. Kalinin (1875-1946), A. S. Makarenko (1888-1939), V. A. Sukhomlinsky (1918-1970).

The fact that pedagogy has put forward such a large number of major teachers is not accidental. The society with its intensive development of production, science and culture required increasing the literacy of the main producers. Without this, it could not develop. Therefore, the number of educational institutions is growing, the network of public schools that provide the necessary training for children is expanding, special educational institutions for teacher training are opening, and pedagogy is being taught

as a special scientific discipline. All this gave a great impetus to the development of pedagogical theory.

Having emerged as a science about the education of children and youth, pedagogy, as the boundaries of education and the scope of subjective factors in the life of society expand, increasingly become a science about the General laws of educational influence on people of all ages.

All the period of its development, pedagogy was based primarily on education and training.

In turn, education is an educational facet of education, has a scientific-disciplinary and natural essence, representing an integral pedagogical process, during which educational tasks are solved, education and development of students are carried out. This process is primarily two-way. On the one hand, it serves as a training (teacher), who sets out the program material and manages this process, and on the other – students, for whom this process takes the nature of teaching, mastering the material being studied. Their joint activities are aimed at deep and lasting assimilation of scientific knowledge, development of skills and abilities, their practical application, development of creative abilities, formation of a materialistic worldview and moral and aesthetic views and beliefs.

Training should be available to this class, age, and level of development. And all that is available is based on the knowledge that is available in the child's mind, obtained in the process of education, family education, direct reflection of natural and social phenomena, communication with adults and peers, in reading, television programs, movies.

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